

THE CONTENT OF KNOWLEDGE NECESSARY FOR THE TEACHER TO IMPLEMENT INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: In this article, the issue of the content of knowledge necessary for the teacher to implement innovative activities is analyzed scientifically and theoretically.

Keywords: field of psychological-pedagogical knowledge, innovative processes, laws, explanatory theories, innovation, content, analysis, evaluation, task, pedagogical experience, level of innovation, stage, introduction of experience, information acquisition, etc.

The research process can be expressed in the form of two stages:

- dividing the non-standardized list of knowledge into parts; - systematizing the selected knowledge, checking them for completeness and representativeness.

Empirical material obtained with the help of the methodology developed and tested during the research from the division of knowledge into parts became the basis. As a result, we isolated the knowledge used by teachers in the implementation of innovative activities from general secondary schools. This knowledge was analyzed based on the criterion of completeness. Completeness means such a choice of an object's public appearance that it expresses its integrity in a structural form based on empirical criteria.

The systematization of the selected knowledge was carried out using generalized levels. The first and second of these levels are unified (unified) for the selection of necessary knowledge for teachers of different subjects, while the third and fourth levels of generalization of knowledge in the innovative field differ depending on the direction of teacher training.

At the first level of generalization of knowledge, a set of theories united by a common sign was chosen, creating a holistic idea of the significant connections between the laws in different spheres of reality. Thus, the sum of the extracted total knowledge at this level is represented by:

A) the field of methodological knowledge - this includes theories that reveal the laws of innovation, methods of conducting pedagogical research;

B) the field of psychological-pedagogical knowledge-includes theories that reveal and explain the laws of innovative processes;

V) combines a set of theories that reveal the sequence of introduction of methodological knowledge-pedagogical innovations into the teaching process and evaluate their effectiveness;

G) the field of special knowledge - consists of a set of theories explaining the characteristics of pedagogical innovation for a particular subject.

At the second level of generalization, theories are distinguished according to the fact that they reveal the laws of reality in a specific area. Therefore, the second level of knowledge is represented by a specific range of knowledge in the areas specified in advance.

Field of methodological knowledge:

- the scope of knowledge on theoretical methodology: methodology as a system of innovative knowledge and an innovative activity system; methodological support of research activities in the field of pedagogical innovation; methodical analysis of the object and subject of innovative research.

- scope of knowledge on normative methodology: scientific substantiation of the difference between pedagogical innovations and other forms aimed at changing the objective reality; determining the relationship of innovative works to the sciences of the field of pedagogy (characteristics of the purpose, separation of special objects, use of special methods and means of understanding, uniformity of terminology); classification of innovative research into groups, the logic of pedagogical research.

The field of psychological-pedagogical knowledge

- the scope of psychological knowledge combines a set of theories that reveal the psychological processes of innovative activity, mental states and characteristics of a person;

- the framework of pedagogical knowledge represents a set of theories that present the laws of innovative processes of teaching and educating the young generation.

Field of methodological knowledge:

- scope of knowledge on learning and generalization of innovative experience;

- the scope of knowledge on transferring pedagogical innovations to new situations;

- the scope of knowledge on the introduction of innovation using effective teaching methods and tools.

Field of special knowledge:

- the scope of knowledge on the development of pedagogical innovations in order to improve the content of a particular subject;

- the scope of knowledge on the application of innovative ideas for certain academic subjects;
- the scope of knowledge on determining the effectiveness of innovative processes for studying a specific subject.

Further detailing of knowledge is related to the emergence of objects highlighted in each subject area with the help of basic concepts describing the most important aspects of the object of innovation.

Thus, the set of theoretical knowledge necessary for the implementation of innovative activities by the teacher is reflected in three levels of generalization and is a programming document - a standard list, which represents the ultimate goal of developing the "knowledge" indicator.

The next step in the development of the "Knowledge" indicator is to obtain predictive information for compiling the final version of the standard list of knowledge. Expert evaluation method was used during the research to obtain predictive information. The experts were asked to evaluate to what extent the range of knowledge necessary for teachers in the implementation of innovative activities at school is fully expressed in the standard list (in points), as well as their importance for two time periods:

- for today;
- for the future.

The assessment of each of the areas of knowledge by experts and the analysis of this assessment is necessary for the correct distribution of the educational load, the allocation of time for studying a certain subject in the development of curricula, as well as in the educational institution. It allows to determine the direction and level of innovative training of teachers. The results of the expert evaluation analysis are given in the form of a diagram.

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